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Motives behind Moonlighting As Perceived By University Faculty in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Pakistan

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Abstract:

The main objective of this study is to assess the perception of faculty related to moonlighting and its associated motives in public sector universities of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. We have selected our representative sample in two tiers. In the first, we have randomly selected nine universities from three strata which divides universities into urban, semi-urban and rural area universities. In stage two, each of the selected universities (primary sampling units) were further stratified according to the designation of the faculty and a sample of 656 faculty members was selected using simple random sampling with proportional allocation of units' selection. The study found a reliable measure which divided moonlighting into occupation specific and non-occupation specific motives. We could not find any association between moonlighting activity and faculty perceptions of dual job keeping as a means for future income targets, coping financial jolts, as insurance for job security, and/or future savings. However, the faculty think that moonlighting helps in setting up new business, it can help in gaining experience in new occupation, and they just do it out of free available time and not for enjoyment. Study recommends the formalization of dual job holding as gig economy has been evolved with the passage of time and short job contracts are new norms of job markets.

Keywords: Moonlighting, Perceptions, Motives, principal component analysis, higher education institutes, Pakistan.

Introduction

There are multiple reasons behind multiple job holding and one cannot attribute it to a single motive. Not only in developing countries which are thought to trigger multiple job holding, but now moonlighting or multiple job has become a very influential and growing attribute of labour market in developed world (Conen, 2020). It is the growing nature of keeping more than one job, that different studies have been conducted in various regions and from various different perspectives. Majority of the research focusses on pecuniary motives, the financial strain which results into moonlighting (Dickey et al., 2011; Ashwini et al., 2017; Asravor, 2021 for example) while there is less or only theoretical research on non-pecuniary motives (Seema & Sachdeva, 2020).

From a different outlook, (Jehan et al., 2019) finds the needs deficiency of moonlighting faculty and comes to know that moonlighters are more deficient in security, esteem and actualization needs. As moonlighting is done out of certain needs, the means to deal with financial problems tops the list which relates to either financial obligations or financial

hardships of the family. However individual may go for multiple jobs due to his/her non-pecuniary priorities (Ashwini et al., 2017).

According Boheim and Taylor (2004) there are four motives which cause employees to moonlight. Firstly, it is suggested by standard model that employee are hour constrained on their primary job i.e. first job, due to which they cannot earn above it, although they are willing to do so. The issue is related to low earnings at primary job and hence in such a situation moonlighting is done for financial motives. Standard labour-leisure model assumes that people/workers willingly supply more labour but the work is not offered by the employer in primary job (Perlman, 1966). It is because of this non-provision of extra work at primary job that the employee goes for a second job for attaining desired income level (Conway and Kimmel, 1998). As most of the firms have policy of offering a fixed level of pay and work hours (Shishko and Rostker, 1976), any work policy which is divergent from an optimal hours of work as perceived by a utility maximizer worker at his/her given wage will induce him/her towards moonlighting conditioned upon a second job wage which is above his/her reservation wage¹ at first occupation. Secondly, there is another situation in which employees come across unwanted financial jolts (shocks) which may motivate them to look for a second job as an alternative source of precautionary savings (Guariglia and Kim, 2004).

Thirdly there is job portfolio motive where the heterogeneity is the main motive when an employee derives different utilities from primary and secondary jobs (Renna and Oaxaca, 2006). The phenomenon could be looked in view of leisure-choice theory in term of job portfolio motive.

According to this view people have preferences for jobs and heterogeneity of job. To satisfy this

motive, people resort to multiple jobs. This decision does not relate to hours constraint on first job but a desire for different job experience and hence diversity (Baah-Boaten *et al.* 2013). So the supply of labour hours in both first and second job are not the perfect substitutes and the second job is undertaken for reasons other than first job labour work hours (Böheim and Taylor, 2004). Lastly the fourth motive is mostly related to job insecurity. And second job, thus, is taken as an insurance device to cope with the risk of loss of the primary job. It is also a mean of human capital diversification suggested by Panoset *al.* (2009). It is most likely that individual may change job due to skill transferability as a consequence of perfect information (Shaw, 1987).

In Pakistan, no research related to moonlighting higher education has been conducted to the researcher's knowledge, there is also no notable study on primary data for dual job holding. Similarly the motives discussed in the literature are scattered in different papers which is combined in this study and an associative analysis is made to re assess these results in an entirely occupation specific endeavor. The main objective is to find association between moonlighting and various motives and to divide these motives into certain groups for general understandings and policy implications.

¹ Reservation wage refers to that lowest wage rate at which a worker is willing to accept a job. In other words if such job is offered which involves similar type of work and the similar working conditions, but wage rate is lower, would be rejected by the worker.

Literature Review

Shishko and Rostker (1976) investigated the determinants of labour supply to moonlight. They estimated moonlighting supply function while using market and demographic characteristics. They found that the supply of labour to second job increases with an increase in its salary and had falling tendency with primary job earning increase. Jamal

and Crawford (1981) examined the desirable and undesirable notion of moonlighting. Their main objective was the comparison of moonlighters on the basis of need fulfillment. Williams (1993) studied the phenomenon of moonlighting among public school physical education teachers, i.e. realities of moonlighting. Paxon and Sicherman (1994) worked on the dynamics and incidence of multiple job holding in United States. They used data from population survey and from panel study of income dynamics. Conway and Kimmel (1998) studied male labor supplies elasticity. They devised a theoretical model to explain the reasons for moonlighting. Guariglia and Kim (2001) used 5 to 8 rounds of Russian Longitudinal monitoring Survey (RLMS) from 1995 to 1998 for analyzing the dynamics of moonlighting in Russian working-age population. Kimmel and Powell (2001) compared moonlighting in Canada and United States. Macq et al. (2001) reported on income generation and work mix of civil servants of developing countries in health service. The result showed that 87% of respondents kept at least one another job. Although all but two of these in low income countries were receiving salaries more than the richest. Naderi (2003) used the data of statistics centre for Iran to obtain determinants of moonlighting rate in Iranian labour market. According to the author moonlighting has increased from 4.5% in 1994 to 8.9% in 2002. Heineck and Schwarze (2004) studied the determinants of moonlighting in Germany and UK. They utilized the data from Germany and British household panel survey for Germany and UK respectively (SOEP Group; Taylor et al. 2001). Renna and Oaxaca (2006) used a static framework to develop job portfolio model of multiple job holders. They developed model using Stone-Geary utility² function where no constraint is considered. Biglaiser and Ma (2007) examined the consequences of moonlighting focusing on its effect on price, quality and welfare of consumer in private as well as public sector. Zhongmin et al. (2009) studied the determinants of multiple job holding in United Kingdom. They used British household panel survey data from 1991 to 2001. Winter (2010) reported evidences of US teachers' moonlighting. They used US Current Population Survey. The study focused at the determination of teachers' moonlighting and its effect on teacher primary job hours. Dickey *et al.* (2011) studied the individual worker motivation for working a second job for off-shore workers working in the UK North Sea Oil and Gas industry. Socha and Mickael (2011) tested the theoretical predictions of dual practice effects for physician working in public hospitals. They used multi-level mixed model as a remedy of cross sectional and observational data limitation. They used standard logistic regression for estimation. They also used three levels for nesting physician and call it nested random effect model in a hierarchal structure. Baah-Boaten *et al.* (2013) used probit regression model on the data obtained from 1998-99 and 2005-06 national household survey in Ghana. Hyder and Ahmad (2013) studied determinants of dual job holding, the characteristics of such people (moonlighters) and relation between worker's main occupation and second job.

Renna et al. (2013) worked on constrained and unconstrained supply of labour using British household panel survey 1991 to 2008. They developed a unified dual and unitary job holding model. Saxon (2015) debated on moonlighting practice in a more narrative and descriptive terms. He termed it a financial necessity as well as a "lifelong" lesson for medicine professionals while practicing medicine. Brow and Sullivan (2017) compared the effect of moonlighting between teachers moonlighting and teachers do not moonlighting. The teachers were perceiving that there is an adverse effect on their teaching due to moonlighting.

Kisumano and Mbaleka (2017) explored the reasons behind teachers moonlighting in a rural setup; a Christian university, where there was no permission to moonlight. They found that moonlighting result into increase in burnout and work-family conflict.

Koomson *et al.* (2017) in their article, pointed out those teachers' salaries are low which compel them either to take loans or hiring purchases in order to fulfill consumption needs. Their research focused on attrition of teaching staff due to financial stress which they claim has not been given much attention.

Timothy and Nkwama (2017) termed research pertaining to teachers moonlighting as an under studied concept. They studied the determinants of primary teachers moonlighting in Ilala district in Tanzania. Nunooet *al.* (2018) analyzed the relation between moonlighting and employment security in Ghana.

²The Stone-Geary function apply natural log function for modeling utility. It is mainly used for modeling problems which involves subsistence consumption levels.

They focused on the effect that security of job have on the moonlighting practice. (Asravor, 2021) finds no difference for male and female multiple job holders' in terms of dealing financial difficulties which is the due to lower earnings (Covid-19 case). Men value primary job security as second most important motivational factor while women value lowering risk of primary job loss. Primary income, marriage and impacts of covid-19 are push factors for moonlighting whereas the presence of working members in the family and having higher education pulls the moonlighting behavior.

The literature review shows that the earlier research work in relation to moonlighting mainly focused on the determinants of labour supply to moonlight. The location as a variable has proved to be one of the important determinants in this regard. The teachers at school levels were subject of moonlighting in some studies which specifically focused on public sector. Attention was given to the determinants of teachers moonlighting and its effects on primary job hours. Although the research focus was on the determinants of moonlighting but in different context (in most cases on general moonlighting) and mostly on secondary data. It is concluded that teachers of higher Institutes were not a focus of research in this regard in past. Less attention was given to the needs fulfillment as a result of moonlighting. This was a unique idea to know that whether moonlighting fulfills the needs for which it is undertaken, but this has not been researched rigorously in economics.

In Pakistan very less attention has been given to this issue and the only prominent work undertaken was with secondary data with a focus on male moonlighting only. Research on primary data and on various samples needs to be undertaken. This research had been planned to be unique in its own perspective. It is based on primary data and it is occupation specific. It also addresses the psychometric issues related to the concept under study both in relation to its motives and need fulfillment.

Sampling and Methodology

In order to select a representative sample, a multi-stage sampling was used. In the first stage, the population was stratified into rural, semi urban and urban universities. In stage two each of the selected universities (primary sampling units) were further stratified according to the designation of the faculty members i.e. Professor, Associate Professor, Assistant professor, Lecturers and Teaching Assistants. From each stratum sample of individuals were selected using simple random sampling. Then we made use of the stratified random sampling in both stages with proportional allocation of units' selection. The detail is given in table 0.1.

The following sample size selection formula was used for sampling in first stage in which

the number of respondents for each category of teachers was calculated (Mwakaje, 2013).

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2} \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where

n = required sample size

N= Population

e = margin of error which is 5% in this case

The resulted sample size consisted of 98 professors, 60 associate professors, 195 assistant professors, 246 lecturers and 67 teaching assistants were the sample respondents in each category. In order to select sample from each university, proportional allocation method was applied as per given formula (Chaudhry, 2008). The final sample was 656.

$$n_i = \frac{N_i}{N} n \dots\dots\dots (3.2)$$

Where

n = shows the required sample size which is randomly selected from the public sector universities.

N = shows the total number of teacher (each category) i.e. the population size.

N_i = Number of teacher in individual category in theeach university.

n_i= Number of teacher in individual category to be selected from the each university.

Assessment of Perception of Faculty Related to Moonlighting Motives

Table 1 shows the perception of the sampled faculty in relation to the moonlighting. These are perceptive responses which were analyzed through a simple descriptive analysis procedure and then the weighted average score for these items. The item score 1 shows strongly disagree, 2 disagree, 3 neutral, 4 agree and 5 strongly disagree response. The figures were rounded to the nearest number based on rounding rules. Table shows that the item stating that moonlighting will help in achieving household income target was responded neutral as a whole as the MAS value is 3. It can also be observed that the highest number of responses (38%) marked neutral. Similarly the MAS value for “moonlighting acts as coping for temporary financial jolts though higher than 3 (rounded to 3) but not in acceptable range for an agree response and hence we can say that faculty as a whole was undecided of whether moonlighting is a mean to cope temporary financial jolts. The Mean Average Score (MAS) also knows as weighted average score(WAS) values for all the statements are almost 3. And the overall MAS were also neutral. So the perceptive responses of the faculty member show their lake of decision about motives of moonlighting. The statements were directed towards the pecuniary and non pecuniary motives but all were perceived same rather there we can say were no clear perception.

Table No.1:Perception of Faculty Related to Moonlighting Motives

Attribute	Response					MAS/ WAS
	SD	D	N	A	SA	
It will help me in achieving household Income Targets	94 -14.9	82 -13	241 -38.3	126 -20	87 - 13.8	3
Moonlighting acts a coping for temporary financial jolts.	61 -9.7	89 -14.1	181 -28.7	218 -34.6	81 - 12.9	3
I keep second job salary for future saving.	84 -13.3	101 -16	207 -32.9	172 (27.3)	66 -	3

					10.5	
I do not moonlight because of job security insurance	79 -12.5	123 -19.5	239 -37.9	136 -21.6	53 -8.4	3
I Moonlight for experiencing in another occupation.	75 -11.9	137 -21.7	199 -31.6	174 -27.6	45 -7.1	3
Moonlighting help in setting up a new business	74 -11.7	107 -17	212 (33.7)	150 -23.8	87 - 13.8	3
Moonlighting is done by me for enjoyment	127 -20.2	136 -21.6	205 -32.5	116 -18.4	46 -7.3	3
I moonlight because free time is available.	86 -13.7	140 -22.2	165 -26.2	167 26.5)	72 - 11.5	3
Total						3

Source: survey

Note: The values in parentheses are percentages

SD = Strongly Disagree, D= Disagree, N= Neutral, A= Agree, SA= Strongly Agree

Cross Tabulation Analysis

In order to know association between moonlighting and perceptive variables of reasons behind moonlighting, chi square contingency tables were made in SPSS through cross tabulation. In the present case, moonlighting was in two categories as moonlighting and not moonlighting and the items of motives behind moonlighting on a five item likert response from strongly disagree to strongly agree. The data fulfilled the assumptions of chi square. For example, the sampling was random, the observations were independent, the column and row categories were mutually exclusive and no expected cell frequencies were less than 5%. The output and its interpretation are as under:

Moonlighting and Perception related to help from Moonlighting in achieving Household Income Targets

To know about the independence between the perceptions that moonlighting will help in achieving household income targets and the incidence of moonlighting; both the variables were cross tabbed. The results are given in Table 2. There were difference of response from moonlighters and non moonlighters related to this perception. For instance, the frequency of moonlighter strongly disagreeing to the statement was 40, while 54 non moonlighters strongly disagreed to this. On the other side, the frequency relating to strong agreement for moonlighters was high as 56 and low for non moonlighters as 31. Those who were not moonlighting and were neutral were 144 and neutral as well as moonlighter were 97 in number.

Table No.2: CrossTabulation (Moonlight * It will help me AchievingHousehold Income Targets)

Moonlight Status	It will help me in achieving household Income Targets					All
	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	
Not Moonlighting	54	53	144	73	56	380
Moonlighting	40	29	97	53	31	250
Total	94	82	241	126	87	630

Source: Survey

 $\chi^2 = 1.889$ (P value=.756)

As a whole there was found no association between moonlighting and the feeling that moonlighting will help a moonlighter in achieving his/her income targets.

Moonlighting and the Perception that Moonlighting Cope with Temporary Financial Jolt

Table 3 is a cross tabulation between the status of moonlighting and the perception that moonlighting acts as coping for temporary financial jolts. There was a very significant number of non moonlighters who were agree to this statement, counted as 127 as compared to moonlighters whose count was 91.

Table No.3: Cross Tabulation (Moonlight * Act as Coping for Temporary Financial Jolts)

Moonlight	Act as coping for temporary financial jolts					All
	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	
Not Moonlighting	39	52	110	127	52	380
Moonlighting	22	37	71	91	29	250
Total	61	89	181	218	81	630

Source: Survey

 $\chi^2 = 1.378$ (P value=.947)

But the neutral count for non moonlighters was 110 and for moonlighters were 71. There was a distinct difference between strongly agree comments from both the groups. More response was observed (i.e. 52) from non moonlighters than moonlighters (29 responses). The test of association i.e. chi square value of 1.378 was found statistically insignificant showing independence of the state of moonlighting and the perception that it will act as coping for temporary financial jolts.

Moonlighting and the Perception that the Moonlighting Salary is kept for Future Saving

Table 4 shows the cross tabulation of moonlighting state and the statement that I keep second job for future saving. Those who did not moonlight were agree by 95 count and strongly agree by 37 count as compared to 61 disagree and 49 strongly disagree. Moonlighters count for agreement was 77 and strong agreement was 29. There were 35

moonlighters who were strongly disagree and 40 disagree. A noticeable number of non moonlighters were neutral accounting for 138 responses while 69 moonlighters were neutral about this statement. The chi square statistics for this joint frequency distribution was statistically non significant which show that there is no association between status of moonlighting and the statement that its salary is kept for future savings and we can say that moonlighting is independent of future saving. It can be the case that moonlighting salary is used while other incomes are saved.

Table No.4: Cross Tabulation (Moonlight * I Keep Second Job Salary for Future Saving)

Moonlight	I keep second job salary for future saving					All
	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	
Not Moonlighting	49	61	138	95	37	380
Moonlighting	35	40	69	77	29	250
Total	84	101	207	172	66	630

Source: Survey $\chi^2 = 5.982$ (P value=.200)

Moonlighting and the Perception that Moonlighting is not done because of Job Security Insurance

Table 5 is cross tabulation contingency table for the association between moonlighting status and the perception that moonlighting is not done for job security insurance. The joint frequency for both the status shows difference of opinions. Those who do not moonlight and were strongly disagree to the statement were 46 in number and those who agree were 33. Similarly the number of disagree moonlighters were 48 and non moonlighters were 75 as compared to the neutral 87 moonlighters and 152 non moonlighter. There was no such difference for strong disagreement on the part of both non moonlighters and moonlighters but a difference of 26 between moonlighters (55) and non moonlighters (81). The chi square value for the association is insignificant statistically which shows there is no association between moonlighting and the perception that it is not done for job security reasons (this rejects Dickey *et al.*, 2011 and is consistent with Heinck and Schwarze, 2004). We can conclude that moonlighting is associated with job security insurance. It may be the case that faculty is not surer of the continuity of their primary job and second job is kept as a safeguard.

Table No.5: Cross Tabulation (Moonlight * Do not Moonlight because of Job Security Insurance)

Moonlight	Do not Moonlight because of Job Security Insurance					All
	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	
Not Moonlighting	46	75	152	81	26	380
Moonlighting	33	48	87	55	27	250
Total	79	123	239	136	53	630

Source: Survey $\chi^2 = 4.082$ (P value=.395)

Moonlighting and the Perception that Moonlighting is done for Experience in Another Occupation

The motive behind moonlighting can be varied. One of the non monetary motives for moonlighting is experience in another occupation. Table 6 shows such case. The responses of non moonlighters were somewhat interesting from the moonlighters' point of view. Their responses both in agreement and disagreement were more than moonlighters even their number in case of neutral count (126) was higher than moonlighters (73), a total 199 count in neutral response. Strongly disagree non moonlighters were 50 and strongly agree were 27 as compared to moonlighters who were 25 strongly disagree and 18 strongly agree. For the disagreement, the count for non moonlighters were double as those of the moonlighters i.e. 92 compared to 45 while less difference in case of agree response. The association between the moonlighting status and the statement that it is a mean for experience in another occupation was statistically significant. Hence it can be inferred that moonlighting has a non monetary motive that it is a mean for gaining experience in another occupation.

Table No. 6: Cross Tabulation (Moonlight * Experience in another Occupation)

Moonlight	Experience in another Occupation				Strongly Agree	All
	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree		
not Moonlighting	50	92	126	85	27	380
Moonlighting	25	45	73	89	18	250
Total	75	137	199	174	45	630

Source: Survey $\chi^2=14.246$ (Pvalue=.007)

Moonlighting and the Perception that Moonlighting is done for Help in setting up a new Business

Moonlighting has another motive of help in setting up a new business. Table 7 shows the cross tabulation statistics. It shows that there were more strong agree responses from non moonlighter teachers (50) than the moonlighters teachers (24) whereas disagree count for non moonlighter was 58 and moonlighter were 49. The neutral count by non moonlighter teachers was 147 as compared to 65 moonlighters. There was more agree response i.e. 86 from non moonlighters than moonlighters (64). The number of moonlighters in the sample was less than the non moonlighters for the present study. That is why non moonlighters' responses are 380 as a whole and moonlighters 250. The independence of both the variables was tested through chi square statistics which signified the presence of association. So we can say that moonlighting is associated with help in setting up a new business.

Table No.7: Cross Tabulation (Moonlight * Help in Setting up a New Business)

Moonlight	Help in Setting up a new Business					All
	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	
Not Moonlighting	50	58	147	86	39	380
Moonlighting	24	49	65	64	48	250
Total	74	107	212	150	87	630

Source: Survey

$\chi^2= 19.784$ (P value=.001)

4.4.7 Moonlighting and the Perception that Moonlighting is done for Enjoyment

Table 8 is a summary of the joint frequency distribution of the moonlighting status and the statement that it is done for enjoyment. The highest count was 129, a neutral response from the non moonlighters followed by disagree response from the same group. The count of neutral response from moonlighters was 76 followed by disagree response as 57 and agree as 45. Strongly agree response was similar for both the groups (23). The measure of association was found statistically insignificant with chi square value of 3.014 and hence it can be said that there is no association between moonlighting and its status as enjoyment.

Table No.8: Cross Tabulation (Moonlight * Working for Enjoyment)

Moonlight	Working for enjoyment					Total
	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	
Not Moonlighting	78	79	129	71	23	380
Moonlighting	49	57	76	45	23	250
Total	127	136	205	116	46	630

Source: Survey

$$\chi^2 = 3.014 \text{ (P value} = .556)$$

Moonlighting and the Perception that Moonlighting is done because Free Time is Available

The perception that a faculty has free time and invests it in moonlighting is considered one of the non monetary motives behind moonlighting. The joint frequency distribution is given in Table 4.56. It shows that non moonlighter teachers who were indifferent to this statement were 102 and moonlighter as 63. Those who disagree were 89 non moonlighters and 51 moonlighters and the count for strong agreement by moonlighters was 37 and moonlighters 34. There was found significant association between the free time availability and moonlighting. It may be the case that faculty takes time in which there is no class engagement as free and hence invests it in secondary job or teaching job is not hectic and time after the regular university schedule is also invested easily. In most of the cases, the private institutes offers classes on weekends or in evening shift and teachers of public sector universities invest their time for earning in a secondary job.

Table No.9: Cross Tabulation (Moonlight * Because Free Time is available)

Moonlight	Because free time is available					Total
	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	
Not Moonlighting	62	89	102	90	37	380
Moonlighting	24	51	63	77	34	250
Total	86	140	165	167	71	630

Source: Survey $\chi^2 = 12.154$ (P value = .033)

4.5 Construct Validity for Moonlighting Construct (Questionnaire)

The study developed a construct by combining various items from previous studies in an eight items on a five point likert scale. The main aim was to understand the psychometric motivation behind moonlighting. The questions pooled were as per the economic theory and mostly comprising of the motives suggested by Böheim and Taylor (2004) stating that moonlighting is done for financial motives, moonlighting is done for unwanted financial jolts (Guariglia and Kim, 2004), an employee derives different utilities from

primary and secondary jobs (Renna and Oaxaca, 2006). The fourth motive is mostly related to job insecurity and a mean of human capital diversification suggested by Panoset *al.* (2009). It is most likely that individual may change job due to skill transferability as a consequence of perfect information (Shaw, 1987). For finding whether our construct is valid the Chronbach's alpha statistics was used.

The acceptable value for Chronbach ranges from .60 to .80 (Clark and Watson, 1995) which signify that the items as a group complement each other to measure a main variable or quality (Litwin, 2003, p. 22). McMillan and Schumacher (2001) have suggested the alpha value to be .70 and above and below this limit, the items must be dealt with utmost care. There is another method to judge the internal consistency by examining item to scale correlations as well as inter item correlations (DeVellis, 2003). Item to scale significance is a measure of construct validity and items are positively related with each other. Clark and Watson (1995) suggested that the average inter-item correlation should be between .15 and .50. Table 10 shows that the questions constructed were reliable with a Cronbach's alpha value of .738.

Table No. 10: Measure of Reliability for Moonlighting Scale

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
0.738	8

Source: Survey

Table 11 shows the item to scale relation in terms of Cronbach's alpha. The statistics of Cronbach's alpha if item deleted shows that all the items fit best for the scale and no item on its deletion will improve the alpha statistics. Hence all the items are best fit for the moonlighting scale.

Table No. 11: Inter Item Status of Moonlighting Scale and Item Relation

Item-Total Statistics	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
It helps me achieving household income targets	21.0492	25.093	.382	.722
Act as coping for temporary financial jolts	20.828	23.920	.533	.692
I keep second job salary for future saving	21.041	24.215	.486	.701
Experience in another occupation	21.133	25.175	.426	.713
Help in setting up a new business	20.987	24.048	.492	.699
Working for enjoyment	21.385	26.282	.289	.738
Because free time is available	21.093	23.621	.506	.696
Do not moonlight because of job security insurance	21.158	26.035	.346	.727

Source: survey

If we look at the inter item and item to scale correlations (Table 12), we find that there is a significant relation between each item and the scale (Here scale refers to the combined score from all the eight items (statements)). It is evident that each item was strongly correlated to the scale. The exception of item no. 7 “I moonlight for enjoyment” all the items were positively correlated with each other. Statements that “I moonlight for enjoyment and moonlighting helps me achieving household income targets were found as negatively correlated, but the relation was statistically insignificant and hence no deviation from the rule. It shows that every perception of a faculty regarding moonlighting is related to every other perception and a faculty thinks about moonlighting in a combined manner. These results of correlation matrix show that these items have strong relation with the scale (questionnaire) and every statement contributes to it in an effective manner. This questionnaire can be used for assessing the perceptive responsive related to moonlighting satisfactorily.

Table No. 12: Moonlighting Inter Item Correlations

		A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	Scale
A	Pearson Correlation	1	.601**	.408**	.130**	.128**	.157**	-.010	.225**	.560**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.001	.001	.000	.797	.000	.000
	N	630	630	630	630	630	630	630	630	630
B	Pearson Correlation	.601**	1	.451**	.346**	.227**	.207**	.068	.302**	.672**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000	.000	.086	.000	.000
	N	630	630	630	630	630	630	630	630	630
C	Pearson Correlation	.408**	.451**	1	.259**	.209**	.248**	.133**	.321**	.638**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000	.000	.001	.000	.000
	N	630	630	630	630	630	630	630	630	630
D	Pearson Correlation	.130**	.346**	.259**	1	.245**	.219**	.132**	.171**	.516**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.000	.000		.000	.000	.001	.000	.000
	N	630	630	630	630	630	630	630	630	630
E	Pearson Correlation	.128**	.227**	.209**	.245**	1	.523**	.170**	.304**	.583**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.000	.000	.000		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	630	630	630	630	630	630	630	630	630
F	Pearson Correlation	.157**	.207**	.248**	.219**	.523**	1	.344**	.367**	.645**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	630	630	630	630	630	630	630	630	630
G	Pearson Correlation	-.010	.068	.133**	.132**	.170**	.344**	1	.412**	.478**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.797	.086	.001	.001	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	630	630	630	630	630	630	630	630	630
H	Pearson Correlation	.225**	.302**	.321**	.171**	.304**	.367**	.412**	1	.661**

	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	630	630	630	630	630	630	630	630	630
Scale	Pearson Correlation	.560**	.672**	.638**	.516**	.583**	.645**	.478**	.661**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	630	630	630	630	630	630	630	630	630

Source: Survey

** show significance at 5%

Note: A shows the statement: it helps me achieving household income targets

B shows the statement: acts as coping for temporary financial jolts

C shows the statement: I keep second job salary for future saving

D shows the statement: I do not moonlight because of job security insurance

E shows the statement: Experience in another occupation

F shows the statement: Help in setting up a new business

G shows the statement: I moonlight for enjoyment

H shows the statement: Because free time is available

The above mentioned justifications are enough to accept the developed scale as valid and reliable. As far as the number of items (statements) are concerned, researchers are agree on three items per scale as absolute minimum and for more reliability the increased items will increase the scale reliability (Spector, 1992) and hence the construct can be assessed for principal component analysis.

Principal Component Analysis of Moonlighting Construct (Questionnaire)

In order to know the most influencing items, the constructed questionnaire was analyzed through principal component analysis. The communalities satisfy the condition for principal component analysis (i.e. communalities must initially equal to 1). These all initial communalities are 1 which is a precondition that communalities values must be close to one. These ones were used as prior communality estimates.

Table No. 13: Factor Analysis of Moonlighting Scale Communalities

Communalities	Initial
It help me achieving household income targets	1.000
Act as coping for temporary financial jolts	1.000
I keep second job salary for future saving	1.000
Do not moonlight because of job security insurance	1.000
Experience in another occupation	1.000
Help in setting up a new business	1.000
Working for enjoyment	1.000
Because free time is available	1.000
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.	

Source: survey

In table 14 it is evident that only two components had Eigen values greater than one which is also confirmed by scree plot. The first component consisted of 27.38% and the second for 26.36% of variance in the construct.

Table No. 14: Factor Analysis using Principal Factor Analysis as Extraction Method

Total Variance Explained						
Component	Initial Eigen values			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	2.865	35.816	35.816	2.191	27.387	27.387
2	1.435	17.937	53.753	2.109	26.366	53.753
3	.942	11.770	65.523			
4	.830	10.380	75.903			
5	.600	7.496	83.399			
6	.546	6.822	90.220			
7	.433	5.407	95.627			
8	.350	4.373	100.000			

Source: survey

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Figure 1: Scree Plot

Table 15 shows that four factors are loaded on component 1 with its factor loading more than or equal to .40 for this component and less than 0.40 for the other component. This component was named as occupation specific component. The other four factors loaded on component 2 and were subsequently named as non occupation specific component of moonlighting.

Table No. 15: Rotated Component Matrix^a

Items		Component	
		1	2
Occupation specific	it help me achieving household income targets	.827	-.038
	Act as coping for temporary financial jolts	.852	.118
	I keep second job salary for future saving	.687	.230
	Do not moonlight because of job security insurance	.400	.307
Non occupa	Experience in another occupation	.184	.655
	Help in setting up a new business	.156	.770

	Working for enjoyment	-.090	.709
	Because free time is available	.288	.649

Source: Survey

Table No. 16: Component Transformation Matrix

Component	1	2
1	.727	.687
2	-.687	.727

Source: Survey

Sample Adequacy and Sphericity Tests

Both KMO and Bartlett's tests showed goodness of data. Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy test value varies from 0 to 1. In present case it is .7 which is acceptable. A value closer to 1 is ideal. Hence sample size was adequate and sphericity (hypothesis that correlation matrix is identity matrix and all the diagonal elements are 1) was found acceptable.

Table No. 17: KMO and Bartlett's Test for Moonlighting Construct

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.724
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	1152.550
	Df	28
	Sig.	.000

Source: Survey

literature cited

- [1] Ashwini, A., Mirthula, G., & Preetha, S. (2017). Moonlighting Intentions of Middle Level Employees of Selected IT Companies. *International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics*, 114(12), 213–223.
- [2] Asravor, R. K. (2021). Moonlighting to survive in a pandemic: Multiple motives and gender differences in Ghana. *International Journal of Development Issues*, ahead-of-print (ahead-of-print). <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJDI-08-2020-0180>
- [3] Baah-Boateng, W., P. Adjei and D.A. Oduro. (2013). Determinants of Moonlighting in Ghana: an Empirical Investigation. *African Review of Economics and Finance* 4(2); 176-202
- [4] Baba, V. V., and M. Jamal. (1992). How much do we really know about Moonlighters? *Public Personnel Management* 21(1); 65-73.
- [5] Bell, D., R. A. Hart, and R. E. Wright. (1997). Multiple job holding as a 'Hedge' against Unemployment. CEPR Discussion Paper No. 1626.
- [6] Berman, P., and D. Cuizon. (2004). Multiple public private jobholding of health care providers in developing countries: an exploration of theory and evidence. London: Department for International Development Health Systems Resource Centre.
- [7] Betts, S.C. (2006). The decision to Moonlight or Quit: incorporating multiple jobholding into a model of turnover. *J Organ Cult Comm Conflict*. 10; 63-78.
- [8] Biglaiser, G., and M.C. Albert. 2007. Moonlighting: Public service and Private Practice. *RAND Journal of Economics* 38(4); 1113-1133
- [9] Boheim, R., and M. P. Taylor. (2004). And in the evening she's a singer with the band: Second jobs, plight or pleasure? IZA Discussion Paper No. 1081. Bonn, Germany: Institute for the Study of Labor.
- [10] Brown, S.M., and S. Sullivan. (2017). Moonlighting and Morale: The Impact on

- Educators Who Moonlight and How Classroom Teaching Suffers. The Journal of Multidisciplinary Graduate Research Volume 1, Article 8, 1-17
- [11] Burch, K.L. (1966). An investigation of the status of the male secondary school teacher in Jefferson County, Kentucky, in relation to additional jobs. *Dissertation Abstracts International*, 27, 1535A. (University Microfilms No. 66-12, 641)
- [12] Bureau of Labor Statistics. (1999). The Employment Situation: News Release. United States Department of Labor.
- [13] Card, D., and R. B. Freeman. (1993). *Small Differences that Matter: Labor Markets and Income Maintenance in Canada and the United States* Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1993.
- [14] Casari, P. (2010). *Labour supply on Brazil: An analysis of the second job in the Urban and Rural areas. Srie de Tetos Para Discussão do CURSO DE ciências Economicas Texto Para Discussão N. 19.* UFG/NEPEC/FACE.
- [15] Champion, J.S. (2010). *Teachers Moonlighting increased accountability and effort.* PhD Dissertation: <http://purl.stanford.edu/nn311fs6634>.
- [16] Champion, J.S. (2011). *America's Teachers: Do Management Practices in Public Schools provide incentives for quality Teaching? A dissertation submitted to the graduate school of business and the committee on graduate studies of Stanford University.* <http://purl.stanford.edu/nn311fs6634>.
- [17] Chaudhry, M.S. (2008) *Introduction to Statistics 3rd edition.* Ilmi Kutab Khana Lahore.
- [18] Chiang, H. (2009). "How accountability pressure on failing schools affects student achievement." *Journal of Public Economics* 93(10): 1045-1057
- [19] Clark, L. A., and D. Watson. (1995). Constructing validity: Basic issues in objective scale development. *Psychological Assessment*, 7:309-319.
- [20] Conway, K. S., and J. Kimmel. (1998). Male labor supply estimates and the decision to moonlight. *Labour Economics*. 5: 135-166.
- [21] Conen, WS (2020) *Multiple jobholding in Europe: structure and dynamics*, WSI Study 20. Düsseldorf: Hans-Böckler-Stiftung.
- [22] Culler, S. D., and G.J. Bazzoli. (1985). The Moonlighting Decisions of Resident Physicians. *Journal of Health Economics*. 4(3); 283-292.
- [23] DeVellis, R. F. (2003). *Scale development: Theory and applications (2nd Edition)*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications, Inc.
- [24] Dickey, H., Watson, V., & Zangelidis, A. (2011). Is it all about money? An examination of the motives behind moonlighting. *Applied Economics*, 43(26), 3767-3774. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00036841003724403>
- [25] Dickey, H., and I. Theodossiou. (2006). Who has two jobs and why? Evidence from rural coastal communities in West Scotland. *Agricultural Economics*. 34(10): 291-301.
- [26] Dickey, H., W. Verity, and Z. Alexendros. (2011). Is it all about money? An examination of the motives behind Moonlighting. *Applied Economics*. 43(26): 3767-3774, DOI:10.1080/00036841003724403
- [27] Divocky, D. (1978a). Moonlighting: Occupational habit or benefit? *Learning*, November. 40-45.
- [28] European Commission. (2002). *Employment in Europe 2002. Recent trends and prospects.* Report by the Directorate-General for Employment and Social Affairs.
- [29] European Union Information Website: EurActiv. (2010). Flexicurity: Europe's employment solution? Available at: <http://www.euractiv.com/en/print/socialeurope/flexicurity-europe-employment-solution/article-169840>.
- [30] Farber, H. S. (1998). Are lifetime jobs disappearing? Job duration in the United States: 1973-1993. In *Labor Statistics Measurement Issues* (eds. J. Haltiwanger, M. Manser, and R. Topel). Chicago, IL: University of Chicago Press.
- [31] Folay, M. (1997). Multiple job holding in Russia during economic transition. Centre discussion paper No. 781
- [32] Gregg, P. and J. Wadsworth. (1999). Job tenure, 1975-98. In *The State of Working Britain* (eds. P. Gregg and J. Wadsworth): Manchester University Press.
- [33] Gregg, P., and J. Wadsworth. (1996). Mind the gap, please? The changing nature of entry jobs in Britain. LSE Discussion Paper 303, Centre of Economic Performance.
- [34] Gregg, P., and J. Wadsworth. (1995). A short history of labour turnover, job tenure, and job

- security, 1975-93. *Oxford Review of Economic Policy*. 11: 73-90.
- [35] Guariglia, A., and B.Y. Kim . (2001). The dynamics of moonlighting; what is happening in Russia. Institute of Economics in Transition. BOFIT. Discussion paper 2001.No.5. Bank of Finland.
- [36] Guariglia, A., and B.Y. Kim .(2004). “Earnings Uncertainty, Precautionary Saving and Moonlighting in Russia”. *Journal of Population Economics*. 17: 289-310.
- [37] Gumm, G.H. (1968). Salary supplementing activities of male public school teachers in Tennessee. *Dissertation Abstracts*, 29, 3799-3800A. (University Microfilms No.69-71, 60)
- [38] Hanushek, E.A., and E. R. Margaret.(2005). Does school accountability lead to improved student performance? *Journal of Policy Analysis and Management* (John Wiley & Sons, Ltd.) 24(2): 297-327.
- [39] Harrison, B. 1998. The dark side of flexibility. *Challenge* 41; 117-127.
- [40] Heckman, J. J.(1979). Sample selection bias as a specification error". *Econometrica*. 47 (1): 153-61. [doi10.2307/1912352](https://doi.org/10.2307/1912352). [JSTOR 1912352](https://www.jstor.org/stable/1912352).
- [41] Heckman, J.J. (1976). *The Common Structure of Statistical Models of Truncation, Sample Selection, and Limited Dependent Variables and a Simple Estimator for Such Models*," *Annals of Economic and Social Measurement*. 5: 475-492.
- [42] Heineck, G. (2003). New estimates of multiple job holding in the UK. Department of Economics, University of Bamberg, Feldkirchenster 21, Bamberg, D-96045, Germany.
- [43] Heineck, G., and J. Schwarze.(2004). Fly me to the moon. The Determinants of multiple Job holding in Germany and UK. 12A discussion paper No. 1358.
- [44] Hicks, V., and O. Adams. (2000). The effects of economic and policy incentives on provider practice. World Health Organization Geneva.
- [45] Hyder, A., and M.A. Ahmad.(2009). The Dynamics of Moonlighting in Pakistan. *The Pakistan Development Review*. 48(4): 497-507
- [46] Hyder, A., and M.A. Ahmad.(2011). The Dynamics of Moonlighting in Pakistan. 25th AGM and Conference of PSDE, 16th- 18th March, 2010 Islamabad, Pakistan Institute of Development Economics. Also available at: <http://ssrn.com/abstract=1875061>.
- [47] International Labour Organization. (2014). Global Wage Report 2014/15 | Asia and the Pacific Supplement from Government of Pakistan Statistics Division: Labour Force Survey (2014).
- [48] Irfan, M.(2008). Quoted by Hyder, A., and M.A. Ahmad.(2011). The Dynamics of Moonlighting in Pakistan. 25th AGM and Conference of PSDE, 16th- 18th March, 2010
- [49] Jacob, R.T., S. Stone and M. Roderick. (2004). Ending Social Promotion: The Response of Teachers and Students. Publication, Chicago, IL: Consortium on Chicago School Research.
- [50] Jacqueline A. (1993). Teacher moonlighting: interviews with Physical Educators *Williams Journal of teaching in Physical education* 13; 62-71. Human kinetics publishers. Inc.
- [51] Jamal, M. ()1986. Moonlighting: Personal, Social, and Organizational Consequences. *Human Relations*. 39(11): 977-990.
- [52] Jamal, M., and R.L. Crawford.(1981). Moonlighters: A product of deprivation or aspiration? *Relations Industrials* 36; 325-335.
- [53] Jamal, M., V.V. Baba and R. Riviere.(1998). Job stress and well-being of moonlighters: The perspective of deprivation or aspiration revisited. *Stress Medicine* 14(3); 195-202.
- [54] Jehan, N., Khan, H., & Arif, M. (2019). Happy Supplying? An Overview of Moonlighting by University Teachers. *Global Economics Review*, 4(1), 22-32.
- [55] Kisumano, G.M., S.W. Mbaleka. (2017). Moonlighting as a growing phenomenon: a case study of a Congolese Christian university. *International Forum Journal*. 20(2); 237-253.
- [56] Koomson, I., B. Afful, and R.A. Villano, (2017). Relationship between Financial Stress, Moonlighting and Teacher Attrition. NESRA Working Paper (nesra/wp/17/005). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=2995561>
- [57] [Kimmel, J and Conway, K. S. \(2001\). "Who moonlights and why? Evidence from the SIPP". *Industrial Relations*. 40\(1\): 89-120.](#)
- [58] Kimmel, J and Powell, L.M. (1999). “Moonlighting Trends and Related Policy issues in Canada and the United States”, *Canadian Public Policy*, vol. 25, issue 2, pp. 207-231
- [59] Krishnan, P. 1990. The Economics of Moonlighting: A Double Self-Selection Model. *Review of Economics & Statistics*. 72(2): 361-367.
- [60] Laffont, J.J. (2003). The principal agent model: the economic theory of incentives.

- Cheltenham: Edward Elgar publishing.
- [61] Lakhani, H., and S.S. Fugita.(1993). Reserve/Guard retention: Moonlighting or patriotism? *Military Psychology*. 5(2): 113-125.
- [62] Laura, M. 2010. "Teachers, Forced to Moonlight." *therecoverytimes.com*, November 2, 2010.
- [63] Litwin, M. S. (2003). *How to assess and interpret survey psychometrics*, 2nd edition. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications, Inc.
- [64] Macq, J., P. Ferrinho, D.V. Brouwere and V.W. Lerberghe.(2001). *Managing Health Services in Developing Countries: Between the Ethics of the Civil Servant and the need for Moonlighting: Managing and moonlighting*, *Human Resource for Health Development Journal (HRD)*. 5(1): 17-24.
- [65] McCullagh, P., and J.A. Nelder. (1989). *Generalised Linear Models 2nd edition* London Chpman and Hall
- [66] McMillan, J. H. and S. Schumacher.(2001). *Research in education: A conceptual introduction*. New York: Longman
- [67] Mortkowitz, L. (2010). "Teachers, Forced to Moonlight." *therecoverytimes.com*, November 2, 2010.
- [68] Mott, P. E. (1965). Hours of Work and Moonlighting. In C. E. Dankert, F. C. Mann, and H. R. Northrup (Eds.), *Hours of Work* New York, NY: Harper & Row: 76-94.
- [69] Naderi, A. (2003). Determinants of moonlighting rate in Iranian labour Market. *Proceeding of the 10th ERF conference*, 16-18 December 2003, Marrakech, Morocco.
- [70] Neumark, D. (2000). Changes in job stability and job security: A collective effort to untangle, reconcile and interpret the evidence. NBER Working Paper No. 7472, Cambridge, MA: National Bureau of Economic Research.
- [71] [Nunoo, J.](#), [D.N. Darfor](#), [K. Koomson](#), and [A. Abigail](#).(2018). Employment security and workers' moonlighting behavior in Ghana. *Journal of Economic Studies*. 45(1); 144-155, <https://doi.org/10.1108/JES-04-2016-0074>
- [72] O'Connell, J. F. (1979). "Multiple Job Holding and Marginal Tax Rates," *National Tax Journal* . 32(1): 73-76.
- [73] Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development.(1997). *Employment Outlook 1997*.
- [74] Panos, A.G., K Pouliakas and A.Zangelidis.(2009). *The Inter-Related Dynamics of Dual Job Holding, Human Capital and Occupational Choice* IZA DP No. 4437 September 2009.
- [75] Partridge, M. (2002). Moonlighting in a high growth economy: Evidence from U.S. state-level data. *Growth and Change*. 33(4): 424-452.
- [76] Paxon, H.C., and N. Sicherman.(1994). *The dynamics of dual job holding and job mobility*. Working paper No. 4968. National Bureau of Economic Research. 1050. Massachusetts\ Avenue Cambridge MA 02138.
- [77] Perlman, R. (1966). Observations on overtime and moonlighting. *Southern Economic Journal*. 33(2): 237-244.
- [78] Perrella, V. C. (1970). Moonlighters: their motivations and characteristics. *Monthly Labor Review*. 93(8): 57-64.
- [79] Pratt, J.W., and R.J. Zeckhauser. (1991). *Principals and agents: the structure of business*. Harvard Business School Press.
- [80] Renna, F. and R. L. Oaxaca.(2006). *The economics of dual job holding: A job portfolio model of labor supply*. IZA Discussion Paper No. 1915. Bonn, Germany: Institute for the Study of Labor.
- [81] Renna, F., and F.R.Oaxaca.(2006). *The economics of dual job holding: a job portfolio model of labor supply*. IZA Discussion paper No. 1915 @ www.econstor.EU
- [82] Renna, F., L.R. Oaxaca and C. Chung.(2013). *Constrained vs Unconstrained labour supply: The Economics of Dual job holding*. CEPS/INSTEAD Working paper No 2013-03 March 2013.
- [83] Robinson, H. and J. Wadsworth.(2007). "Impact of the Minimum Wage on the Incidence of Second Job Holding in Britain". *Scottish Journal of Political Economy*. 54(4);553-574.
- [84] Rouse, C.E., H. Jane, D. Goldhaber and D. Figlio. (2007). "Feeling the Florida heat? How low-performing schools respond to voucher and accountability pressure." NBER Working Papers 13681. National Bureau of Economic Research.
- [85] Saxon, J.T. (2015). Moonlighting Pros and Cons for Fellows. *J Am Coll Cardiol*. 65(2):214-

- [86] Seema., and Sachdeva. G., (2020).Ashwini, A., Mirthula, G., &Preetha, S. (2017). Moonlighting Intentions of Middle Level Employees of Selected IT Companies. *International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics*, 114(12), 213–223.
- [87] MOONLIGHTING INTENTIONS OF I.T. PROFESSIONALS: IMPACT OF ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT AND ENTREPRENEURIAL MOTIVATION. (2020). *Journal of Critical Reviews*, 7(02). <https://doi.org/10.31838/jcr.07.02.38>
- [88] Shah, M.A. (2014). Rural wages rise across Asia, decline in Pakistan: report. The News.Friday, October,2014 From Print Edition
- [89] Shaw, K.L.(1987). Occupational Change, Employer Change, and the Transferability of Skills, *Southern Economic Journal*. 53 (3): 702-719
- [90] Shishko, R., and B.Rostker.(1976). The Economics of Multiple Job Holding," *American Economic Review*. 66 (3): 298-308.
- [91] Sikes, P.J. (1985). The life cycle of the teacher.In S.J. Ball & I.F. Goodson (Eds.), *Teachers' lives and careers*.London: Falmer Press. 27-60.
- [92] Smyth, G.K. (1996). Regression modeling of quantity data with exact zeroes.Proceedings of the Social Australia-Japan workshop on stochastic models in Engineering, Technology and Management.Technology Management center. University of Queensland: 572-580
- [93] Socha, K. and B. Mickael. (2011). The relationship between dual practice and physician work behavior in the public hospitals: results from the Danish survey. *Health Economics Papers* 2011:1, University of Southern Denmark.
- [94] Spector, P.E. (1992). *Summated rating scale construction: An introduction*. Newbury Park, CA: Sage.
- [95] Stewart, C.W. (1981). The conditions related to and the effects of multiple jobholding on fulltime teachers (Doctoral dissertation, University of Iowa). *Dissertation AbstractsInternational*, 42, 4655A
- [96] Taylor, D. E., and E.S. Sekscenski.(1982). Workers on long schedules, single and multiple jobholders.*Monthly Labor Review*. 105(5): 47-53.
- [97] Timothy .V. L. and S. Nkwama.2017. Moonlighting among teachers in urban Tanzania: A survey of public primary schools in Ilala District *Cogent Education* 4: 1334434 <https://doi.org/10.1080/2331186X.2017.1334434>
- [98] Tucker, M.L. (19650. A study of salary-supplementing activities of Utah public school teachers.*Dissertation Abstracts*, 26, 184. (University Microfilms No. 65-7592)
- [99] Tweedie, M.C.K. (1984). An Index which distinguishes between some important exponential families. In *Statistics: Applications and new directions*. Proceeding of Indian Statistical Institute Golden Jubilee International Conference. Pp 579-604. Calcutta. Indian Statistical Institute.
- [100] Wilensky, H. L. (1963). The Moonlighter: A Product of Relative Deprivation. *Industrial Relations*3; 105-124.
- [101] Williams, J.A. (1992). Moonlighting: The norm for physical educators.*The Physical Educator*, 49(1); 14-22.
- [102] Winter, V. J. (2010). Teachers Moonlighting: evidence from the US Current Population Survey. *Applied Economics letters* 17; 1111-1114
- [103] Wisniewski, R., and P. Kleine. (1983). Teacher moonlighting: An unstudied phenomenon. Paper presented at the annual meeting of the American Education Research Association, Montreal, Canada.
- [104] Wisniewski, R., and P. Kleine. (1984). Teacher moonlighting: An unstudied phenomenon. *Phi Delta Kappan*.65: 553-555.
- [105] Wu, Z., M. Baimbridge and Y.Zhu. (2008). Multiple job holding in the United Kingdom: Evidence from the British household panel survey. Nottingham Trent University Working Paper 2008/1.
- [106] Zhongmin, W., M. Balmbridge and Y.ZU.(2009). Multiple Job holding in the United Kingdom; Evidences from British Household panel survey. *Applied Economics*. 41(21): 2751-2766